

The Rejection of Divine Temptation: A Study in the Arian Heroism of *Paradise Regained*

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Abstract: John Milton reforms scriptural conceptions of heroism in *Paradise Regained* through his Arian displacement of Jesus from the traditional Christian Trinity. Accordingly, I propose that his revisions of the New Testament serve his rebellion against the prescriptions of scholastic prelates, thus connecting his late masterpiece to his early anti-scholastic tracts. Jesus, like the poet Milton, can justify the ways of God to readers through his independent responses to Satan's scholastic temptations. Only through Jesus's assertion of subjective interpretations of scripture can he achieve a level of tolerant heroism in the face of hegemonic prescriptions.

Furthermore, in this paper I propose that Satan's implicit temptation for Jesus to perceive himself as divine runs parallel to the prescriptive intolerance of scholastic prelates. I assert that Milton's portrayal of Satan as a scholastic like Athanasius and Jesus as an independent thinker like Arius reveals his push for the toleration of subjective interpretations of scripture. *Paradise Regained* is Milton's revival of the tolerance of the classical world. I propose that Milton created an iconoclastic Arian hero capable of inspiring readers to tolerant thought in rejection of authoritative prescription.

Keywords - John Milton, literary criticism, Arianism, *Paradise Regained*, religious tolerance.

I. INTRODUCTION

John Milton undoubtedly attempts to reform scriptural conceptions of heroism throughout *Paradise Regained* through his radical displacement of Jesus from the traditional Christian Trinity. Although much of the scholarship on Milton's *Paradise Regained* and *Christian Doctrine* has focused on his heretical Arianism, there is still much to be explored in Milton's corrections of what he believed to be corruptions of the New Testament. In *Paradise Regained*, Jesus, like the poet, being closer to God, can justify the ways of God to readers through his wholly human, completely rational responses to Satan's wily temptations and wonderfully perverse discourse. Only through Jesus's externalization of independent human intuition through dialogue with an interlocutor can he achieve a level of heroism unprecedented in the New Testament. Thus, Jesus's bravery lies in his human obedience to, and the externalization of, his own intuition, as previously elucidated by the indispensable critic Marshall Grossman in his "Poetry and Belief in *Paradise Regained*, to which is added, *Samson Agonistes*."

I propose that in addition to Satan's overt temptations of Jesus throughout *Paradise Regained*, a close reading of the text reveals Satan's implicit temptation for Jesus to perceive himself as fully divine, which could not hold up in Milton's theological system. If Jesus were to renounce his humanity and perceive himself as a divine part of the Holy Trinity, this would remove his altruistic human agency. To give into Satan's subtle, scholastic, and sophisticated temptation of the divine would dismantle Jesus's ability to participate in dialogue, simultaneously nullifying his capacity for intellectual agency. The narrative of *Paradise Regained* absolutely hinges upon Jesus's refusal to perceive himself as divine, fulfilling Milton's revisionist masterstroke: the creation of a distinctly iconoclastic Arian hero.

II. Milton's Christology

To what extent was Milton's Christology influenced and shaped by the beliefs of Arius? Is this question of any true significance for contemporary Milton scholars? Milton's theological opposition to include Jesus within the traditional Christian Trinity carries great weight; indeed, the debate over his religious heresy on the topic of the Trinity has been a lively one extending as far back as Jonathan Richardson's 1734 defense of Milton's orthodoxy.

To best address these questions, it is important to recognize that Milton's heterodox view of Christ is not merely an *academic* question. As Michael Lieb aptly notes in his *Theological Milton*, "those who held heterodox beliefs (especially Antitrinitarian beliefs) during Milton's time faced the real possibility of imprisonment and death" (262). Additionally, Rowan Williams, author of *Archetypal Heresy: Arianism through the Centuries*, claims that Arianism was regarded as "the archetypal Christian deviation, something aimed at the very heart of the Christian confession... [Arianism was] irrevocably cast as the other in relation to Catholic (and civilized) religion" (73). In the ecclesiastical art of The Middle Ages, Arius was often depicted alongside the figure of Judas, implying his role as the consummate betrayer of Christ and subsequently of *Christian* belief. Nevertheless, it must be noted that Arius himself never conceived a coherent or authoritative ideology. Arianism was fabricated by a polemical Nicene writer named Athanasius, who developed the term to the purpose of countering heretical developments within the early church (74). Despite the fact that Arianism is not a monolithic phenomenon with a well-articulated doctrine developed by the historical figure of Arius, I employ Milton's view of Christ as a belief in line with this fabricated, and much maligned, concept of Arianism, to further develop the importance of Christ as a non-divine human figure in *Paradise Regained*.

How can Milton be viewed as an Arian when he praises the "Trinal Unity" in *On The Morning of Christ's Nativity*, and concludes his anti-prelatic tract *Of Reformation* with a hymn of triumph praising that "one tri-personal Godhead" (832)? The only proper answer scholars may attain is that somewhere along the line Milton's beliefs changed; he would later contradict these early statements with several rejections of Trinitarian beliefs both in his late poetry and prose. The following passage from *Paradise Lost* illustrates a fascinating delineation between The Son and Godhead:

when at the holy mount
Of Heav'n's high-seated top, th' imperial throne
Of Godhead, fixed forever firm and sure,
The Filial Power arrived and sat him down
With his great Father, for he also went
Invisible, yet stayed (such privilege
Hath omnipresence) and the work ordained,
Author and end of all things, and from work
Now resting (7.584-591).

Brilliantly, Milton inserts a vision of Jesus outside of, but privileged by, God's omnipresence. Additionally, Milton showcases his turn to Antitrinitarianism during the second chapter of his prose masterpiece *Christian Doctrine*, where he emphasizes the ninth attribute of God as "one" or a single unification. To back up his claims, Milton cites proof texts from the Old as well as the New Testaments. Kerrigan, Rumrich, and Fallon note that "this authority of the scripture he buttresses with appeals to reason: the simplicity of the Bible, the mathematical concept of oneness, and the axiom that God cannot be involved in anything that implies a contradiction" (1150). During the fifth chapter of *Christian Doctrine* Milton elucidates this point further:

If he [Jesus] did derive his essence from the Father, let my opponents prove how that essence can be supremely divine or, in other words, one with and the same as the

Father's essence... For the divine essence, which is always one, cannot possibly generate or be generated by an essence the same as itself... For a supreme God is self-existent, but a God who is not self-existent, who did not beget but was begotten, is not a first cause but an effect and is therefore not a supreme God (1188).

J.N.D. Kelly states that the fundamental premise upon which Arian doctrines are based is “the affirmation of the absolute uniqueness and transcendence of God, the unoriginal source [agennetos arkhe] of all reality” (32). If this acknowledgement of one God who is eternal, pre-dating existence, alone without beginning or origin, alone possessing immortality, and alone the judge of all, is the fundamental aspect of Arianism which excludes the possibility of a divine Son, then it is undeniable that this doctrine can be reconciled with Milton’s theological view of Jesus as the “one just man” existing outside of the Trinity. Moreover, this doctrine can be reconciled both with a God that is “one first matter all” and Milton’s belief that the soul dies with the body (432). Even if Milton’s theological view of godhead is singular, differing from that of Arius (if *Arius* can even be called an “Arian” for that matter), the purpose of this paper is *not* to create a perception of Milton as having an unqualified affiliation to any one systematic theology over another; after all, as Lieb states: “Milton’s attempt to distinguish between Father and Son on the metaphysical grounds of *essentia* and *substantia* [in his *Christian Doctrine*]” is contrary to Arian doctrine which makes no distinction between the two. Instead, the purpose of this paper is, through a deep analysis of *Paradise Regained*, to ascribe Arian theology to Jesus in order to assert that his strictly human composition is absolutely integral to his heroic refusal of Satan’s temptations.

Whether or not Milton personally had a strict allegiance to Arianism, throughout the theological system artistically rendered in *Paradise Lost* and *Paradise Regained*, Milton’s God is unique, transient, and indivisible, and his divinity cannot be shared or communicated directly. The essence of God cannot be imparted to Jesus within this system: this would imply God is divisible, mutable, and knowable. Instead, Milton’s one God brings Jesus into existence from nothing, and although Jesus enjoys an exalted station, he is a finite creature, a human of a different order of existence than God; in fact, according to the Arian doctrine that holds up in Milton’s system, “The Father remains ineffable to Jesus, and the Word can neither see nor know the Father perfectly and accurately” (74). Thus, it is justifiable to perceive Jesus as being subject to the same sinfulness, mutability, and temptation, as the rest of humanity in the post-lapsarian realm of *Paradise Regained*. Whether or not the concepts of Arianism fit neatly into the foundations of *Paradise Regained* fails to eradicate the fact that Jesus’s denial of Satan’s temptations throughout *Paradise Regained* hinges on Milton’s conception of Jesus as fully human. Indeed, if Jesus were not susceptible to moral mutability or sinful temptation, he would hardly be perceived by Milton’s audience, or conceived by Milton himself for that matter, as the hero of this brief epic.

Just as the Jesus of *Paradise Regained* represents Milton’s human ideal, a man of faith, temperance, and adherence to scripture to whom God is “ineffable,” conversely, let us now consider the idea that *Satan* is Milton’s embodiment of the kind of scholastic sophistry that was in direct opposition to the toleration of opinions based on scripture which Milton believed in and championed. In his *Milton’s Arianism: why it matters*, John P. Rumrich succinctly notes that Milton’s characterization of Arian beliefs in *Of True Religion* (1673) is illustrative of his own eventual turn away from the Trinity:

The Arian and Socinian are charg’d to dispute against the Trinity: They affirm to believe the Father, Son, and Holy Ghost, according to Scripture, and the Apostolic Creed; as for terms of Trinity...and the like, they reject them as Scholastic Notions, not to be found in scripture, which by a general Protestant Maxim is plain and perspicuous abundantly to explain its own meaning in the proper words, belonging to so high a Matter and so necessary to be known; a mystery indeed in their sophistic Subtilties, but in Scripture a plain Doctrine (VIII.424-25).

Rumrich aptly recognizes that both Milton and Locke “firmly and consistently rejected what they regarded as excessive, speculative reasoning embodied in customary church doctrines” (79). Just as Milton’s own thought progresses from anticlericalism and an Arminian toleration stance to the “serious consideration” and eventual “endorsement of antitrinitarian tenets” through his *Christian Doctrine*, *Paradise Regained*’s Satan embodies the very same scholastic intolerance of opinions based on scripture that led Milton to personally adopt antitrinitarian views.

III. Analysis of *Paradise Regained*

Satan tempts Jesus to accept the idea of a “Trinity” that does not originate from biblical scripture, coercing Jesus to engage in “excessive, speculative reasoning” about the nature of his own power: speculative thought that Milton viewed as characteristic of the senselessness of scholastic sophistry. Satan may be perceived as an embodiment of Milton’s anticlericalism as voiced in *Of Reformation* and his other anti-prelatic prose works: an embodied figure that a rational, liberated, *human* being, Jesus, has the power to reject through his dialectical and faithful adherence to the hermeneutic process. It is important to note here that in *Paradise Regained* Milton speaks of Jesus and not of “The Son.” Milton purposefully omits “The Son” since neither Jesus nor Satan fully recognizes that Jesus is, in fact, The Son. Both Satan and Jesus must discover through dialectic that Jesus is “The Son” and that Jesus as “The Son” is not God. Yet Satan would prefer Jesus to identify himself as equivalent to God, for he would then surrender the altruistic agency of his rational argument.

Jesus of *Paradise Regained* simplifies the nature of God by stressing a preference for scriptural evidence over arbitrary human authority and dialectical reasoning over Satan’s metaphysical complications. Like a true scholastic thinker, Satan brings these metaphysical complications into trade in a manner not unlike the sophistries of Athanasius, implicitly tempting Jesus to further question the nature of his own existence as opposed to adhering to his individual faith in the will of God. Instead of depending on interpretive prescriptions similar to those of the bishops and ecclesiastic authorities of Milton’s own time, Jesus adheres to his individual interpretation of the Bible, refusing to question why he is led into the wilderness. To re-state his own words, “I am let / Into this wilderness, to what intent / I learn not yet, perhaps I need not know; / For what concerns my knowledge God reveals” (1.290-93). An absolute self-reliance on intuition in terms of Biblical hermeneutics is essential to Jesus’s powerfully human authority over Satan.

Jesus cannot predict the future, as he is not all-knowing, divine, or omniscient: he is simply a human being who refuses to intuitively falter in the face of the prelatic prescription. “Who brought me hither / Will bring me hence, no other guide I seek” (Milton *PR* 1.335-36), Jesus proclaims in response to a disguised Satan during their first encounter in the desert, rejecting the excess of prelatic guides for spiritual interpretation and guidance. “By miracle he may [bring you hence]” (1.337), Satan replies, a brief statement that carries much weight, emphasizing both Satan’s anxiety, fear, and mistrust in the divine will of God, and his temptation for Jesus to perceive himself as a divine force capable of performing miracles beyond his mortal capacity. Subsequently, this mention of miracle reflects the perversity of Satan’s inner desire for Jesus to be truly divine, a part of the Trinity capable of miracles, perhaps so he cannot be truly ashamed if his temptations fail. For if Jesus is truly a part of God, there is no possibility that he would ever give into Satan’s temptations. If Jesus were truly divine or *perceived* himself as truly divine, then in Satan’s eyes his own failure to tempt Jesus would be quickly forgiven by his hellish crew in Pandaemonium.

“If thou be Jesus of God, command / That out of these hard stones be made thee bread” (1.342-33), Satan urges, tempting Jesus to display his presumed supernatural powers, urging him to transubstantiate rocks into food for his own sustenance. Satan, in the true scholastic form of Trinitarian-endorsing prelates, questions “a mystery indeed...in Sophistic subtleties [which is] in Scripture a plain Doctrine” (1188). Jesus need not indulge in such excessive supernatural ruminations, for man lives not only by bread, but by the word of God laid down in the scripture, which he intuitively to be true through human intuition, adheres to, and finally brings into trade through reasoned discourse.

The power that Jesus displays here was received through individual and learned experience with the scripture: “The law of God I read, and found it sweet, / Made it my whole delight, and in it grew / To... perfection” (I.207-209) Jesus declares in Book I, and only after he has profoundly contemplated the laws of God through his individual study and interpretation of the scripture can he bring what he has learned of faith into rational discourse.

After his rationalistic interpretations of the scripture, Jesus “held it more humane, more heav’nly, first / By winning words to conquer willing hearts, / And make persuasion do the work of fear” (I.221-22), which emphasizes that Jesus has chosen to interpret the Bible in a “humane” way in accordance with his human capacity for willful interpretation. Jesus denies the presence of divinity within him here, choosing a humane path of rational discourse over the shock and awe of theophany; thus, he outright chooses to perceive himself as a rational human being as opposed to a divine entity. Additionally, his knowledge of what is most “humane” was not divinely imparted to Jesus but acquired through independent study. What is best known was gained through his interpretation of scripture, but that alone is not enough: what is gained through our individual interpretations of the Bible must then be exhibited, and tested, through rational dialogue with an interlocutor. Thus, it is God’s plan, or Milton’s for that matter, “To exercise him in the wilderness” (I.156) in order for Jesus to put what he has learned to trade through the completely human act of discourse. Passages like these throughout *Paradise Regained* exemplify Milton’s illustration of how reason is reconciled with faith.

Satan’s recognition of the legitimacy of oracles throughout the dialogue suggests his preference for interpretive authorities existing outside of the biblical source material. This reflects for Milton another example of the popish episcopacy on Satan’s part through his defilement of the original purities of the Christian tradition. “Men generally think me much a foe / To all mankind: why should I?” Satan asks Jesus in Book I. Soon after, Satan claims that with mankind he dwells “Copartner in these regions of the world, / If not disposer; lend them oft my aid, / Oft my advice by presages and signs, / And answers, oracles, portents and dreams, / Whereby they may direct their future life” (I.392-96). Here Satan explicitly represents the episcopacy, misguiding the experience and initiative of individual thinkers and interpreters of the Bible, perverting their initiative by manipulating, or claiming to manipulate, the various mechanisms of nature. Much like the false prescriptions of prelates, Satan steps into the deceptively false role of intermediary between humanity and divinity, providing mankind with erroneous oracles, predictions, and ideas beyond those set down in the scripture. Much like Athanasius and his idea of the Holy Trinity, Satan confounds individual thinkers, preys upon their fear of God, and asks them to buy into the excessive metaphysical questioning of nature that they need not ask. Indeed, Satan’s excessive questionings, sophisticated interpretations of events to come, and subsequent imposition of these predictions onto humanity, combined with his distrust in the unfolding of divine events, reflect the cowardice of the episcopacy in *Paradise Regained*. Under the episcopal government, according to Milton:

the obscene and surfeited priest scruples not to paw and mammock the sacramental bread as familiarly as his tavern biscuit...[the episcopacy is] a swollen tumor...a bottle of vicious and hardened excrements...a heap of hard and loathsome uncleanness, [which is] to the head a foul disfigurement and burden. (822).

Whereas Jesus is indicative of the former modesty and republican spirit of the early bishops and fathers who pointed to scripture as the ultimate Christian authority, Satan embodies the vile corruption of false authority stemming from the church representatives who penned the episcopal texts that were for Milton “at times contradictory and at times corrupt” (Kerrigan, Rumrich, Fallon 806).

As Barbara Lewalski illustrates in *The Life of John Milton* regarding Milton’s early anti-prelatical tracts:

His basic argument is the fundamental Protestant principle that scripture alone must determine all matters of religion, including liturgical practice and church government or “discipline.”... [Milton] instead appeals

continually and often explicitly to the “spirit” of the gospel. By the standard of the wholly spiritual, humble, and egalitarian ministry instituted by Christ he finds the episcopal institution an abomination, meriting his almost visceral disgust. But his concept of a ministry without coercive power or tithes or any function not open to the laity, and his emphasis on all God’s people as prophets distance him from Presbyterianism, with its clerical authority, tithes, and repression of dissent. Milton is moving, even at this stage, toward Independency...Milton sees and presents himself in these tracts as a learned scholar, but one whose essential characteristic is an intellectual independence neither constrained nor needing support from human authorities (122).

By the publication of *Paradise Regained* in 1671, roughly thirty years after his early tracts against the bishops, Milton had finally moved completely toward “Independency” in terms of his religious convictions, yet the principles upheld and argued through the dialogue between Jesus and Satan in *Regained* illustrates what Lewalski, in the passage above, illuminates regarding Milton’s early attitudes. Jesus undoubtedly embodies the humble and egalitarian tolerance of faith throughout *Paradise Regained*, while Satan embodies the “coercive power” of the episcopacy, yet I must press further here and assert that there are some aspects of the young John Milton in the Jesus of *Paradise Regained*: Jesus asserts an “intellectual independence neither constrained nor needing support from human authorities” (122). As we have already seen Satan embody the corrupt human authorities of the episcopacy, we can now reasonably perceive Milton himself to be embodied by the Jesus of *Paradise Regained*, the learned scholar of scripture who asserts his independent interpretation of the Bible over the false prescriptions of episcopal authorities. Jesus, much like the early Milton who championed tolerance for the individual’s interpretation of scripture, seeks “no other guide” for his experience with the Bible (I.336).

As “other guides,” the oracles in Book I of *Paradise Regained* can be interpreted to be symbolic of the false claims made by prelate and scholastic texts which Milton himself abhorred, thus equating the falsehood of Satanic persuasion to the pomp and excess of the episcopacy. These prelate oracles are trumped by Jesus, the individual human interpreter of the Bible, who claims that “No more shalt thou by oracling abuse / The Gentiles; henceforth oracles are ceased / God hath now sent his living oracle / Into the world, to teach his final will, / And sends his Spirit of Truth henceforth to dwell / In pious hearts, an inward oracle / To all truth requisite for men to know” (I.455-464). It is important to note that the “Spirit” of Truth that Jesus mentions here in Book I of *Paradise Regained* is tantamount to and coeval with, the “spirit” of the gospel which Milton “appeals continually and often explicitly to” (122) in his anti-prelate tracts. This “spirit” is pure, humble, individualistic, and egalitarian: the exact opposite of the traits Milton applies to the prelates who crammed their prescribed interpretations down the throats of worshippers in the same way that Satan presents false oracles to mankind.

A close reading of Jesus’ trumping of Satan’s oracles reveals that the “spirit” of individual interpretation and intuition regarding scriptural meaning dwells “in pious hearts, an inward oracle / To all truth requisite for men to know” (I.463-64); thus, Milton proves to himself, and to his readers as well, that each human being harbors his or her *own* “inward oracle,” and, therefore, possesses his or her own capability to independently read and interpret scripture in a manner untainted by prelate authority in order to attain pure, pious, and true enlightenment. Moreover, this reading attaches a new layer of meaning to the opening passage of *Paradise Regained* where we find that “Recovered Paradise to all mankind” is given “By one man’s firm obedience” (I.3-4). In this interpretive light, all of us can implement our own “inward oracles,” put our individually perceived truths into trade toward the purpose of recovering hints of the prelapsarian past. True obedience in *Paradise Regained* becomes defined by strict adherence to one’s “inward oracle.” In the face of this willful, liberated individualism, Satan, like a true episcopal, shirks away, “amazed” and “dissembled” (648).

At this point I must shift the focus of my critical endeavor to Book II of *Paradise Regained* where we find Satan in Hell expressing his curious concerns regarding the true nature of Jesus.

Confounded with an excess of metaphysical questions as to the nature of Jesus' being, Satan ignorantly assumes that in order for Jesus to possess "amplitude of mind to greatest deeds" he must be "with more than human gifts from Heav'n adorned" and inherently contain "perfections absolute" and "graces divine" (II.137-38). Conversely, Jesus is faced with the human trait of hunger: he even dreams "as appetite is wont to dream, / Of meats and drinks, nature's refreshment sweet" (II.264-65). At this point in the narrative, Satan again asks for a divine explanation that goes beyond the limits of scripture: "How hast thou hunger then?" (II.319) displays Satan seeking a supernatural cause for the mental fortitude of Jesus.

Subsequently, Satan offers up handsome youths, wine, Naiades, and "spirits of air, and woods, and springs, / Thy gentle ministers, who come to pay / Thee homage, and acknowledge thee their Lord" (II.374-76), yet Jesus does not acknowledge the "homage" of those who acknowledge him as their "Lord"; in fact, he refuses to respond to this temptation of accepting divine worship, instead giving all the glory to God, the "one first matter all" who is the true *essentia* of the divine. Jesus responds accordingly as an obediently humble human being submissive to God's path of necessity: "Thy pompous delicacies I contemn, / And count they specious gifts no gifts but guiles" (II.390-91). The gift of divine worship is correctly identified by Jesus as merely an effort of guile on Satan's part, just as the scholastics and prelates tempted the humble, temperate, obedient worshippers of God with the excessive pomp of Trinitarian belief.

The final temptation of Book II arrives as soon as the table of pomp vanishes: earthly glory. "What hope dost thou aspire to greatness?" (II.417-18) Satan asks, reminding Jesus that as a poor son of a carpenter, "unknown, unfriended, [and] low of birth" (II.413), he lacks Earthly fame. If Jesus were to perceive himself as divine or seek out worshippers and attain wealth in pursuit of worldly honor and false friendships, he would remove his capacity for the intellectual agency while erasing his own ability to defend his individual beliefs manifested through discursive argument. If this were the case, Satan would win by default, dissembling faith from reason, oppressing individual interpretive belief just as Milton believed prelates sought to take away the individual freedom of interpretation by prescribing excessive doctrines beyond those apparent in scripture. As opposed to accepting himself as a part of the divine Trinity, Jesus rejects "the crown, / Golden in show...but a wreath of thorns / [that] Brings dangers, troubles, cares, and sleepless nights / To him that wears the regal diadem" (II.458-61), preferring instead the wisdom and virtue possessed by human beings who adhere to they're uniquely subjective interpretations of scripture.

As Book III begins, Satan is unready to give up on his temptation of supernatural power and divine glory. He continues this strain of temptation:

Or wert thou sought to deeds
That might require th' array of war, thy skill
Of conduct would be such, that all the world
Could not sustain thy prowess, or subsist
In battle, though against thy few arms.
These godlike virtues wherefore dost thou hide?
Affecting private life, or more obscure
In savage wilderness, wherefore deprive
All earth her wonder at thy acts, thyself
The fame and glory, glory the reward (III.16-25).

Satan tempts Jesus to showcase his supernatural power and to use this power to subjugate the human race that would then honor and worship him as God. Despite this temptation, for Jesus, "what delight to be by such extolled, / To live upon their tongues and be their talk, / Of whom to be dispraised were no small praise?" (III.54-56) By refusing to be worshipped, Jesus places himself outside of the Trinity through his dialogue with an interlocutor, displaying his human obedience to, and the externalization of, his intuition. This, as evidenced by Marshall Grossman, is the true "heroism" of *Paradise*

Regained, and this brand of heroism is within the confines of Arian thought: to make Jesus perceive himself as divine would be a form of pompous idolatry, making Milton just as vulgar as the scholastic prelates he vehemently opposes.

Refusing war and conquest, Jesus discovers his true identity: a wise, true, temperate human being who aspires to a kind of glory that “may by means far different be attained / Without ambition, war, or violence; / By deeds of peace, by wisdom eminent, / By patience, [and] temperance” (III.89-92). This passage displaying Jesus’s denial of violent and glorious ambition reflects his refusal of prelatic ideas and his adherence to the word of God; indeed, the perverse desire to seek fame through amending and supplementing excessive metaphysical theories to scripture is analogous to using divinity as a means to achieve the ends of the earthly glory.

Although Satan’s corrupt poetic ornamentation of geographical and historical panoramas in Book III reflects the temptation of earthly experience and glory, what most supports my reading of *Paradise Regained* during this Book is Satan’s temptation of Jesus to impulsively conquer humanity, to bring humankind to servitude under the oppression of divine force, and to supremely reign over the human world. Nonetheless, Jesus does not recognize himself as possessing any power beyond human capability and seeks no oracular prediction of events; nor does he seek any explanation of, or addendum to, God’s promise of his eventual reign. Jesus responds, “Means I must use thou say’st, predication else / Will unpredict and fail me of the throne: / My time I told thee (and that time for thee / Were better farthest off) is not yet come” (III.394-97), exhibiting firm patience and adherence to the word of scripture above the ambiguous, anxious, and impatiently predictive theorizing tendencies of the prelates.

After refusing to acknowledge the possibility of employing divine power to the ends of forcefully conquering and reigning over humanity, Jesus condemns the idolatrous tribes that Satan suggested he dominate. “No, let them serve / Their enemies, who serve idols with God” (III.431-32) Jesus states. This statement is ironic, for in addition to condemning idolatrous acts Jesus refuses to make *himself* an object of idolatrous worship by rejecting the theoretical possibility of a divine conquest; Jesus refuses to view himself as a part of the holy Trinity. Milton has figured his own ideological stance into his Jesus through this refusal to allow mankind to idolatrously worship a human being as an object of divinity, for as Milton states in his prose work *Christian Doctrine*, to worship Jesus “who did not beget but was begotten, is not a first cause but an effect, and is therefore not a supreme God” (1188), would equate an act of heathenish idolatry. Subsequently, when Satan tempts Jesus to worship him as a potential recompense for the prize of Athens, he essentially reiterates his last temptation for Jesus to make an idol out of himself, duplicitously masking the subtle, scholastic appeal of idolatry with a slightly different form, yet in essence, it is the same temptation: effectively, for Jesus to view himself as divine equates the same heresy as would worship Satan. Milton has expressed his own heterodoxy as an absolute truth, effectively flipping orthodoxy on its head through dramatic irony. Thus, Milton transmutes scholastic orthodoxy into heresy while uplifting the truth of his own ideological convictions within the subtleties of his dramatic narrative.

In a definitive moment from Book IV reflective of Milton’s own eventual denial of the idea of the Trinity, Jesus rejects Satan during the following passage:

Wert thou so void of fear or shame,
As offer them to me the Son of God,
To me my own, on such abhorred pact,
That I fall down and worship thee as God?
Get thee behind me; plain thou now appear’st
That evil one, Satan forever damned (IV.189-94).

It speaks volumes that Jesus is compelled to identify Satan by name only after he has attempted to make an idolatrous worshipper out of The Son. Although Jesus has refused this temptation through reasoned discourse, Satan attempts to turn this discourse against him by tempting him with the prospect of Athens, where he can perhaps opportunely refute “their idolisms, traditions, and

paradoxes” through reasoned discourse (IV.234). Nevertheless, Jesus rejects the temptation of Athens due to his acknowledgment that much of the philosophical discourse of Athens has attempted to over-intellectualize the “plain Doctrine” of scripture much in the same way as Athanasius and the scholastic prelates (VIII.424-25). “For all his tedious talk is but vain boast, / Or subtle shifts conviction to evade. / Alas what can they teach, and not mislead; / Ignorant of themselves, of God much more, / ...Much of the soul they talk, but all awry, / And in themselves seek virtue, and to themselves / All glory arrogate, to God give none” (IV.306-15). This passage reflects the overly intellectual theorizing of the scholastic prelates of Milton’s own time as much as it does the philosophy of Stoicism.

For Milton, the prelates, like the Stoics before them, give glory to themselves in selfish and satanic ways, perpetually refusing glory to God. The prelates appropriate sophisticated terms in line with the “Fortune and Fate” of the Stoics, replacing this old jargon with the new terminology of the Trinity. Milton’s major problem with Zeno of Citium is equivalent to his problem with Athanasius: “Who reads / Incessantly, and to his reading brings not / A spirit of judgment equal or superior ...Uncertain and unsettled still remains, / Deep-versed in books and shallow in himself” (IV.322-26). Shallow prescription of how to interpret scripture without the substance of manifestly true or applicative action inevitably leads to corrosive scholastic sophistry and passive subjugation. Accordingly, Milton preferred an active and individualistic study of scripture and advocated for the tolerance of biblical interpretation. To Milton’s mind, it was supremely important for learned people to take it upon themselves to formulate their own ideas through discourse with interlocutors, and to put those ideas into trade to properly test whether or not these ideas can endure in the face of well-crafted opposition. Hence, Milton presents the dialogue of Jesus and Satan as the crux of his brief epic *Paradise Regained*: the battlefield of reasoned discourse is the only true testing ground for ideas.

Despite alluding to The Son’s Arian mortality through his acknowledgement of Jesus as “firm/ to the utmost of *mere man* both wise and good, / Not more” (IV.534-37, *emphasis added*), still perplexed as to the true nature of Jesus as a mortal being, Satan places him atop the highest pinnacle of the Temple of Jerusalem and commands him: “show thy progeny” (IV.554). This act on Satan’s part reveals both his doubt that a mere mortal can stand on the pinnacle and his presumption that a miracle is required and God must provide one. Jesus, who I assert represents Milton in opposition to Satan, his prelatric embodiment, cites the Bible, “Tempt not the Lord thy God,” and Satan falls, mirroring his initial defeat and plummet through Heaven, yet *another* divine location, in *Paradise Lost*. Standing adamantly in the face of temptation, The Son becomes the metaphoric rock that dashes Satan, ultimately fulfilling the Protevangelium. Milton intends his readers to assume that Satan simultaneously recognizes Jesus as The Son of God and a mortal man, and he is thus utterly confounded. While Jesus gives all the glory to God in this moment, Satan has ultimately failed in his temptation of Jesus to accept himself as a divinely glorious part of the Trinity. Within an instant, both Satan and Jesus are granted a “full awareness of his [Jesus’s] divine Sonship” (522).

IV. CONCLUSION

While Satan’s potential victory inevitably demanded idolatry and worship, Jesus stands on the convictions of his own independently realized beliefs, and Milton provides Jesus as a model for the rest of mankind. Undoubtedly, this ending provides comfort for those who lost the revolution in England with the reassurance that the fight will continue underground as “unobserved” as the Jesus we see returning in private to his mother’s house in the final lines of *Paradise Regained*: This is only the beginning for Milton. If the people persist in consulting their inner oracles for truth, continue to resist idolatry and the pomp and regalia of prescribed thought, and persevere in putting forth their self-actuated ideas through reasoned discourse, then they can stand as perpetually firm as Jesus on any pinnacle in the face of the temptation of interpretive homogenization.

When critics re-encounter Milton’s late masterpieces with the intention of uncovering fresh layers of meaning beneath his explicit textual surfaces, important interpretive bridges are capable of being constructed. New parallels are then drawn between the radical, youthful intellectual who composed the anti-prelatric tract *Of Reformation* and the elder master poet of *Paradise Regained*, to

which is added, *Samson Agonistes*. Ultimately, the path to an exceedingly complete grasp of Milton's vision is approached, unveiling the deep thematic link between his progression as a poet and his radical support for the toleration of subjective interpretations of scripture.

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